

Design Guide of a Double Purpose Rain Sampler for Contaminant and Isotope Analysis

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1 | Background

This design presents a rain collector suitable for the simultaneous monitoring of contaminants and stable water isotopes. The main goal of this project was to create a standardized rainwater collector for an interdisciplinary collaboration at the Geography Institute, University of Bern (GIUB). This document serves as an accompanying, clear, and accessible guide that can be implemented as is or used as a foundation for future adaptations. This design guide aims to reduce redundant development efforts by offering step-by-step instructions for both construction and field installation.

This particular rain collector is designed with dual objectives in mind: monitoring both contaminants and isotopes in precipitation. Collecting samples for both analyses with a single collector maximizes efficiency by enabling multiple research objectives to be addressed simultaneously.

For successful contaminant analysis, it is crucial to minimize contact between water and plastic components, as many contaminants can adhere to plastic surfaces (Fatema et al., 2022). To address this, a glass collection bottle is used, which minimizes the risk of contamination or analyte loss. While it would be ideal to use a glass funnel and tubing as well, this is not feasible for outdoor installations due to their fragility. However, the brief contact with plastic components such as the funnel and tubing will be evaluated under controlled laboratory conditions before field deployment to assess any potential influence on sample quality.

To successfully analyze the isotopic content of precipitation, the collector must minimize loss of water to evaporation, as it alters the isotopic signature of precipitation. Various collector designs have been developed to address this issue, all focused on reducing the exposed water surface area. The approach of using an inflatable bag collector to reduce the headspace and exchange with ambient air (Michelsen et al., 2018) cannot be used here due to the necessity of a glass collection bottle. The paraffin-oil and the tube-dip-in-water approach have been shown to result in the least isotopic shift and mass loss (Michelsen et al., 2018). However, considering both practical constraints and the need to avoid potential interactions between paraffin oil and contaminants, the tube-dip-in-water method was selected for this design. This method presents a compromise: placing the tube opening low in the collection bottle ensures it is submerged after the first rainfall, effectively reducing the surface area exposed to the atmosphere and thus limiting evaporation. However, this also increases the contact between water and tubing, which is less ideal for contaminant sampling. The refined positioning of the tubing and whether contact with the tubing influences contaminant behavior will be assessed before deployment. An additional measure to minimize evaporation involves insulating the collector to protect the water sample from temperature fluctuations and direct heat exposure.

The collectors were installed on June 11th, 2025, along an elevational transect between Innertkirchen and Steingletscher (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Positions of installed collectors, STE-NES (46.7149733°N, 8.27803°E), STE-GAD (46.733829°N, 8.382681°E), STE-RIV (46.731565°N, 8.4224467°E) and STE-INLET (46.721895°N, 8.434142°E).

The estimated amounts of rainfall for the planned research site are listed in Table 1. It is intended for biweekly sampling in a temperate climate with monthly precipitation ranging from approximately 105 to 185 mm (Table 1, calculated with data from MeteoSwiss).

Table 1. Estimation of rainfall collection volume based on historical rainfall in Gadmen, Bern, Switzerland (46.73685 N, 8.351136 E, 1190 m ü. M.), based on an assumed biweekly collection period. Blue highlighting shows maximum and minimum volumes.

Station				A (Funnel d = 16cm) = $\pi \cdot r^2 =$	
Gadmen				201.1	
Month	~ cum. P/month; in mm	~ cum. P/2week; in mm	Volume V = $A \cdot x(\text{cm}) / 1000$ in liter		
1	120	60.0	1.21		
2	106	53.0	1.07	min	
3	126	63.0	1.27		
4	117	58.5	1.18		
5	165	82.5	1.66		
6	169	84.5	1.70		
7	181	90.5	1.82		
8	183	91.5	1.84	max	
9	129	64.5	1.30		
10	117	58.5	1.18		
11	120	60.0	1.21		
12	133	66.5	1.34		

2 | Description and Materials

Rainfall is captured using a funnel and collected in a 2-liter glass bottle. The funnel is equipped with a removable sieve to prevent debris or leaves from entering the sample bottle. A funnel diameter of 16 cm was chosen, providing a collection area of 201 cm². This corresponds to expected rainfall volumes between 105 and 185 mm/month (assuming a collection frequency of 1x/month) and ensures that adequate water is collected during periods of low precipitation, while preventing overflow in wetter periods (when using a 2-liter bottle).

Two tubes—one for water, one for air (obligatory to not create a vacuum)—pass through a screw-on cap into the collection bottle. The water is transferred from the funnel via silicone tubing with an inner diameter of 8 mm. Silicone was chosen for its UV resistance, and this tubing size is compatible with GIUB's existing rain gauge, allowing for potential future integration of rainfall measurements. To equalize pressure with the outside atmosphere, a silicone tube (4 mm inner diameter, 1.5 m length) is coiled inside a protective container. Although a longer (e.g., 15 m long) pressure tube can be beneficial (Gröning et al., 2012), this was deemed excessive for current needs. However, if evaporation via the air vent proves too high, the tube can be extended to mitigate this issue.

The collection bottle is enclosed within an insulated container that buffers temperature fluctuations, protecting the isotopic composition from the effects of evaporative fractionation. Styrofoam was chosen for insulation due to its lightweight properties and workability with basic tools. The outer container is a polypropylene box, selected for its durability and practical design—it can be positioned on its side and opened like a door, allowing for quick and easy bottle replacement when collecting the sample. To further reduce solar heating, the exterior can be spray-painted with a reflective coating, if necessary (Gröning et al., 2012).

The collector is self-supporting and can be installed in alpine terrain without requiring additional structural support. To ensure durability and stability, it must be securely anchored to withstand environmental stressors such as wind and storms. A 1-meter steel pole will be driven approximately 50 cm into the ground using a hammer. An aluminum pole will then be placed over the exposed 50 cm, elevating the pole to a height of about 2 meters, to which the funnel will be attached (*Figure A3: Photo 4*). This height helps prevent splashing from the ground. The pole will be secured to the box using a latch, and the box itself can be additionally secured with pegs, ropes, or cable ties— if a nearby fence or similar structure is available. One potential issue is the swaying of the aluminum pole in strong winds, which could affect the collection volume. Ideally, the mouth funnel will remain perpendicular to the direction of rainfall.

Figure 2: Photo 1, Frontal view of rain collector, the funnel is planned to be installed 2 meters above the box.

3 | List of Materials

Productname	Measurements	Material	Source	Product Nr.	CHF
Box "Stöckli Aufbewahrungsbox"	Aussen: 400 x 300 x 220 mm Innen: 363 x 263 x 210 mm	Polypropylen	Bauhaus	30952287	16,10
Lid "Stöckli Deckel zu Normbehälter"	400 x 300 mm	Polypropylen	Bauhaus	30922970	8,10
Insulation "Swisspor Hartschaumplatte EPS 20"	60 x 500 x 1000 mm and 40 x 500 x 1000 mm	Styrofoam	Bauhaus	31243610	5,70 3,80
Pole "Catnic Torstahl"	2000 mm Ø 12 mm	Steel	Bauhaus	13899744	7,30
Aluminium Pipe "Kaiserthal Rundrohr Aluminium"	2000 mm Ø 15 mm	Aluminium	Hornbach	6368942	8,55
Bracket (round) "Stabilit Rohrschelle"	24 x 18 mm	Steel	Bauhaus	10662053	1,10
Aluminium Profil "Kantoflex Winkelprofil"	40 x 40 x 1000 mm, 2mm thick	Aluminium	Bauhaus	10507510	14,20
Funnel with sieve and flexible pipe "Pressol Winkeltrichter"	Ø funnel: 160 mm Ø outlet: 12 mm	Polypropylen	Bauhaus		8,25

Glass Bottle	V = 2l, h = 260 mm, Ø 13 mm	Glass	cLab		
Screwcap "GL 45 screw thread caps"	Ø 21,26 mm	Polypropylen	cLab		
Tubing for Water	Ø inner: 8 mm Ø outside: 12 mm Length: 1700 mm	Silicon	Biochem Materialausgabe		3,80/m
Tubing for Air	Ø inner: 4 mm Ø outside: 7 mm Length: 1500 mm	Silicon	Biochem Materialausgabe		3,00/m
Rivets	Ø 4,8 mm min: 4mm, max: 7mm	Aluminium	Bauhaus	22899503	9,60
Cable Rail "Max Hauri Kabelclips Set 8mm"	Ø 8 mm 10 x10 x 30 mm	Plastic	Conrad	164658	11,95
Double-sided tape "Tesa Powerbond Outdoor"	19 mm x 5m		Bauhaus	15386987	13,55
Pegs	Min length: 200 mm 2 pcs per Collector	Aluminium / Steel			

4 | Assembling the Rain Collector

Working Steps:

1. Prepare Funnel
 - a. Cut out the flexible part of the funnel on both sides, leaving the last bulge.
(see *Figure A1: Photo 2* on page 9)
 - b. Place the upper funnel part into the bottom funnel part (the two bulges fit into each other perfectly, but it might require a bit of force and bending of the plastic, which can be straightened out after).

2. Cut Styrofoam into the following pieces. (see *Figure A6: Sketches 1a:1e* on page 10)
 - a. 40 x 25 x 35 mm → 2 pieces
 - b. 60 x 13 x 25 mm → 1 piece
 - c. 60 x 13 x 29 mm → 1 piece
 - d. 60 x 13 x 17 mm → 1 piece

3. Drill 2 holes into the cap for tubing: the holes must be smaller than the outer diameter of the tubes. (see *Figure A7: Sketch 2* on page 11)
 - a. Ø 10 mm hole for 12 mm tubing
 - b. Ø 6 mm hole for 7 mm tubing

4. Drill holes into the Box
 - a. Top: 1 hole for water tubing, \varnothing 10 mm
 - b. Side: 1 hole for air tubing, \varnothing 6 mm (see *Figure A2: Photo 3* on page 9)
 - c. Back: 4 holes for aluminium profile, \varnothing 4,8 mm (see *Figure A7: Sketch 4* on page 11)
 - d. Back: 2 holes for bracket (round), \varnothing 4,8 mm
 - e. Side: 4 holes for additional attachment, \varnothing 4,8 mm (see *Figure A7: Sketch 3* on page 11)

5. Prepare Aluminium profile (see *Figure A8: Sketch 5* on page 12)
 - a. Cut into approx. 20 cm length.
 - b. Front: Drill 4 holes with the same spacing as holes in the box (\varnothing 4,8 mm).
 - c. Bottom: - drill 2 holes (\varnothing 8 mm) for pegs and
 - drill 1 hole in the exact middle (\varnothing 16 mm) for the Aluminium pole.

6. Attach the bracket and aluminium profile to the box. (see *Figure A7: Sketch 4* on page 11)
 - a. Use rivets and rivet-pliers for attaching to each hole.

7. Place tubings
 - a. Pull the water tube from outside to inside into the box until the end of the tube is approximately 14 cm above the bottom of the box.
 - b. Pull the water tube through the 10 mm hole in the lid until the lid is approximately 2,5 cm below the top of the box.
 - c. Pull the air tube through the lid (until it peaks out approx. 1 cm or even less)
 - d. Arrange the air tube in a suitable and organised way. I used the off-cut of the funnel to pull the tube through 4 times to keep it in a bulk, but any similar piece could be used, or even 2 cable binders to keep the tubing together. (see *Figure A4: Photo 5* on page 9)
 - e. Pull the air tube through the hole on the side until it peaks out approximately. 10 - 15 cm.
 - a. Use the cable rail to guide the air tube: one on the outside of the box and one on the top inside of the box between the cap and the funnel off-cut. (see *Figure A4: Photo 5* and *Figure A2: Photo 3* on page 9)
 - b. Attach the Funnel to the water tubing; it is tight, but it fits.

5 | Testing the rain collector

The rain collector was installed outside for one week, during which three water samples were collected. The sampling period included several light rainfall events. At the beginning of the experiment, the collector was filled with 125 mL of tap water to simulate an initial

water body. Each sample was subsequently analyzed using a laser spectrometer (Picarro, LWIA - L2140i, Santa Clara, CA, USA) to determine the $\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ isotopic composition of the collected water (see Table 2).

Table 2. $\delta^2\text{H}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, and detex values of the collected water samples.

	Sample	date	time	dDmean	d18Omean	detex	rainfall_ml
1	S1	21.03.2025	11:45	-75.77	-10.68	-0.31	0
2	S2	24.03.2025	11:45	-73.31	-10.02	-3.12	90
3	S3	27.03.2025	9:00	-75.09	-10.22	-3.34	50

The results are visualized in Figure 3 ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ versus $\delta^2\text{H}$) and Figure 4 (calculated as lc-excess). Lc-excess is a measure of the deviation of the isotopic composition of water from the LMWL and are calculated with $lc\text{-excess} = \delta^2\text{H} - a*\delta^{18}\text{O} - b$, where a and b are the slope and the intercept of the LMWL (Zhu et al., 2022). Positive lc-excess values typically indicate mixing with meteoric waters, while negative values are associated with evaporation (de la Casa et al., 2022).

Figure 3: This shows the isotopic signatures of three rainwater samples (S1, S2, and S3) in relation to the Global Meteoric Water Line (GMWL) and the Local Meteoric Water Line (LMWL). The GMWL, represented by the red dashed line, reflects the typical isotopic relationship between $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ in precipitation worldwide, with a slope of approximately 8. The LMWL, shown as a blue dashed line, represents the relationship in local conditions.

Figure 4: This shows the sampled values calculated as Ic-excess. The blue dashed line represents the LMWL.

Notably, samples S2 and S3 fall clearly below both the Global Meteoric Water Line (GMWL) and the Local Meteoric Water Line (LMWL), which suggests that evaporation occurred between sampling intervals. The LMWL was determined with a linear regression model using monthly data between 2010 to 2012 for the GNIP station in Bern (46.9521 N, 7.4395 E, 511 m ü. M.) from the Global Network of Isotopes in Precipitation (GNIP) - downloaded through the WISER portal (Water Isotope System for Data Analysis, Visualization and Electronic Retrieval).

One first explanation for this trend is evaporation due to environmental exposure (e.g., solar radiation, ventilation) affecting the collected water before sampling, which would mean that the collector is not performing as well as hoped. A second explanation lies in the isotopic characteristics of the rainfall itself: during low-intensity or intermittent precipitation events, raindrops are subject to kinetic fractionation as they fall through dry air, resulting in lower d-excess/Ic-excess values. This phenomenon has been documented in prior studies, such as Fröhlich et al. (2002), who observed depleted d-excess during small and sporadic rain events in subtropical environments. Further testing under controlled conditions and additional sampling during dry periods (i.e., without any rainfall between two sampling events) are necessary to distinguish between evaporative effects and natural isotopic variability in light rainfall.

6 | Appendix: sketches and photos

Figure A1: Photo 2, connector showing part removed (green lines).

Figure A2: Photo 3, grey box showing where to fasten tubing.

Figure A3: Photo 4, showing installation outside for testing.

Figure A4: Photo 5, showing the curled up air tubing inside the box.

Figure A5: Photo 6, showing the aluminium profile for attachment with pegs.

Sketch 1a: frontal view of inside

Sketch 21b: frontal view of lid

Sketch 1c: 3D view of styrofoam pieces

Sketch 1d: side view of inside + aluminium profile

Sketch 1e: side view of lid

Figure A6: Sketches 1a:1e, showing exact geometry and construction of all parts.

Sketch 2: inside and side view of screwcap

Sketch 3: attachment holes on the side

Sketch 4: aluminium profile and attachment latch

Figure A7: Sketches 2, 3 & 4, showing exact geometry and construction of all parts.

Figure A8: Sketch 5, showing the measurements of the custom made aluminium profile.

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(<https://www.meteoschweiz.admin.ch/service-und-publikationen/applikationen/ext/climate-overview-series-public.html#https%3A%2F%2Fservice.meteoswiss.ch%2Fproductbrowser%2FproductDisplay%2Fclimate-overview-series-public%3Flang=de&cg1.year=2025&cg1.language=de&cg1.location=ALT&cg1.productName=climate-overview-series-yearly>)

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